

Comparison of Assessment and Evaluation Elements of 2018 and 2024 Primary School Mathematics Curriculums

Nur Sirmacı

Atatürk University Kazım Karabekir Faculty of Education

Abstract: *The aim of the study was to compare the assessment and evaluation elements of the 2018 and 2024 Mathematics Curriculums. In this study, the document review method in the qualitative research design was used. The data of this study consists of 2018 and 2024 Mathematics Curriculum. In the research process, documents were first accessed. The originality of the documents was checked and an attempt was made to understand the documents. Then, data analysis was started. In the data analysis, while comparing the assessment and evaluation in the programs, the unit of analysis was determined in accordance with the purpose of the research. In the study, sentences and paragraphs in the curriculum were used as the unit of analysis. As a result of the analysis, necessary information was provided on assessment and evaluation in both programs. However, in the 2024 program, assessment and evaluation types were determined for each subject and presented to the service of practitioners.*

Keywords: Program, Program elements, Assessment and evaluation

1. INTRODUCTION

The primary school mathematics course curriculum aims to ensure that students who complete primary school become individuals who are morally whole and self-aware, self-confident and self-disciplined, who have acquired the basic verbal, numerical and scientific reasoning skills and social skills and aesthetic sensitivity that they will need in daily life, and who are oriented towards a healthy life by using them effectively. Primary school mathematics course curriculum has four elements to achieve these goals.

These elements consist of objectives, content, teaching-learning situations and assessment and evaluation. Each of them has various benefits for students and practitioners. Among these, assessment and evaluation are an important part of every education-training process and the basic element of quality searches in education (Balcı and Tekkaya). Whether the expected benefit from the program is provided or not, whether the knowledge, skills and attitudes of the students are developed or not is determined through assessment and evaluation (Özenç, 2013). Assessment and evaluation is one of the program elements that informs the level of learning that the student has. (Plaza, Draugalis, Slack, Skrepnek, and Sauer, 2007) Various tools are used during assessment and evaluation.. To give examples

of these; self-assessment, peer-assessment, co- assessment, concept maps, rubric, check lists, open ended question, written exam(Mamur, 2010, Katrien Struyven, Filip Dochy and Steven Janssens). Each assessment tool provides teachers with information about the level of learning that students have. Teachers organize their education and training accordingly. In fact, evaluations are made to provide feedback to instructors who want to change their teaching practices (Chen and Hoshower, 2003). Because assessment and evaluation are the answer to the question, "How can the effectiveness of learning experiences be evaluated?" (Dillon, 2009) The questions of curriculum, Journal of Curriculum Studies, 41:3, 343-359).

Therefore, assessment and evaluation must be done very well. Therefore, assessment and evaluation must be prepared and implemented very well. Based on this, the problem of the research was determined as "What are the similarities and differences between the assessment and evaluation elements of the 2018 and 2024 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum?"

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Model of the Research

In this study, qualitative research design and document review method was used. Document review research consists of the levels of document collection, verifying document originality, document understanding, data analysis and data use (Kıral, 2020).

2.2. Research Process

2.2.1. Document Collection :

The data of this study consists of the the Assessment and Evaluation in the 2018 Primary School Mathematics(1., 2., 3.and 4. Grades) and 2024 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum(1., 2., 3.and 4. Grades). The research data were taken from <https://mufredat.meb.gov.tr> and <https://tyymm.meb.gov.tr>.

2.2.2. Verifying Document Originality: Both curriculum examined are official curriculum used in Turkey.

2.2.3. Document Understanding:

The assessment and evaluation statements in both mathematics curriculum were read and interpreted comparatively.

2.2.4. Data Analysis:

The categories titled assessment and evaluation were created for the 2018 and 2024 primary school mathematics curriculum. After the categories were created, the unit of

analysis was determined depending on the purpose of the study. In the study, sentences and paragraphs included in assessment and evaluation were used as the unit of analysis. Finally, findings and results based on the evaluation of the assessment and evaluation elements in both programs in terms of similarities and differences were presented.

In the assessment and evaluation section of the 2018 primary school (1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th grade) mathematics curriculum, there is no assessment and evaluation section for each subject. However, in the assessment and evaluation section of the 2024 primary school (1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th grade) mathematics curriculum, there is a assessment and evaluation section for each subject. For this reason, the assessment and evaluation section of one of the subjects was selected and included in the analysis. The subject selected for analysis is the subject “2. THEME: Numbers and Quantities (2) Numbers and Quantities” in the 2024 Primary School Mathematics Course curriculum (3rd Grade). Information about the subject is provided below.

2. THEME: Numbers And Quantities(2)

In this theme, it is aimed that students can use models to represent whole, half and quarter with fractions; to analyze a whole as a unit fraction to create equal parts; to analyze the relationship between the numerator and denominator of a fraction; to read and write analog and digital clocks; to understand and convert hour, minute and second from time assessment units; to make judgments by estimating the duration of events. In addition, it is aimed that students can recognize centimeter, meter and kilometer from length assessment units; gram, kilogram and ton from mass assessment units and convert them among themselves; to convert our money into coins and paper money according to their values.

4.FINDINGS

Table 1

Assessment and Evaluation in The 2018 Primary School Mathematics Curriculums

No person is exactly the same as another. For this reason, it is against human nature for curriculums and the related assessment and evaluation process to be “suitable for everyone”, “valid and standard for everyone”. For this reason, it is essential to act with the maximum understanding of diversity and flexibility in the assessment and evaluation process. Curriculums are a guide in this respect. Expecting curriculums to include all elements related to assessment and evaluation cannot be considered as a realistic expectation. Since diversity in education is seriously affected by internal and external dynamics such as the individual, education level, course content, social environment, school facilities, etc., the priority in ensuring the effectiveness of assessment and evaluation practices is expected from teachers and educational practitioners, not curriculums. At this point, originality and creativity are the basic expectations from teachers.

-
1. Assessment and evaluation studies should provide maximum compatibility with all components of the curriculum, and the limits of achievements and explanations should be taken as basis.
 2. The curriculum does not draw definite boundaries for implementers in terms of assessment tools and methods that can be used in the assessment process, it only guides them. However, the required technical and academic standards should be followed in the preferred assessment and evaluation tool and method.
 3. Assessment and evaluation practices in education are an inseparable part of education and are carried out throughout the education process. Assessment results are not considered alone, but in an integrated manner together with the processes followed.
 4. Due to the fact of individual differences, it is not appropriate to talk about a single type of assessment and evaluation method that covers all students and is universal for all students. The academic development of the student is not measured and evaluated with a single method or technique.
 5. Education is provided not only for “knowing (thinking)” but also for “feeling (emotion)” and “doing (action)”; therefore, only cognitive assessments cannot be considered sufficient.
 6. Multi-focused assessment and evaluation is essential. Assessment and evaluation practices are carried out with the active participation of teachers and students.
 7. Individuals’ characteristics such as interests, attitudes, values and success, which are the subjects of assessment and evaluation, may change over time. For this reason, it is essential to use assessments that take into account changes in the process rather than measuring these characteristics at a single time.
-

Table 2

Assessment and Evaluation in The 2024 Primary School Mathematics Curriculums

In the Primary School Mathematics Curriculum, skill-based assessment and evaluation processes that will support students' learning and provide systematic feedback to students are taken as basis. The experiences offered to students with learning-teaching practices in the teaching phase have been prepared by taking into account student success and competencies.

These competencies are designed to support field-specific skills as well as social-emotional learning and literacy skills, values, and tendencies, and are designed in accordance with individual differences. The processes of achieving learning outcomes are presented with learning evidence. The learning evidence includes assessment tools used in the assessment and evaluation of learning-teaching processes.

In the Primary School Mathematics Curriculum, feedback is provided to students about their learning levels, deficiencies or misconceptions by using different assessment tools. The assessment tools used in this process are designed to contribute to the teaching process based on feedback. The aim of the program is to develop students' higher-order thinking skills and students' competencies and skills through assessment and evaluation activities.

The program is based on both traditional and alternative assessment and evaluation approaches

that will appeal to different learning styles, and various assessment and evaluation tools are reflected in the applications according to these approaches. Different assessment and evaluation approaches applied throughout the learning-teaching process are included in a way that takes into account the development level of each student. The alternative assessment tools in the program are designed to help students transform the information they learn in the classroom into a skill by transferring it to daily life. The assessment tools used in the assessment and evaluation of learning-teaching processes are included in the learning evidence.

In the Primary School Mathematics Curriculum, feedback is provided to students about their learning levels, deficiencies or misconceptions by using different assessment tools. The assessment tools used in this process are created in a way that will contribute to the teaching process based on feedback. The aim of the program is to develop students' higher-order thinking skills and students' competencies and skills through assessment and evaluation activities. The program is based on both traditional and alternative assessment and evaluation approaches that will appeal to different learning styles, and various assessment and evaluation tools are reflected in the applications according to these approaches.

Different assessment and evaluation approaches applied throughout the teaching-learning process are included in a way that takes into account the development level of each student. The alternative assessment tools in the program are designed to help students transform the information they learn in the classroom into a skill by transferring it to daily life.

Theme 2: Assessment and Evaluation on Numbers and Quantities (2)

Learning outcomes of this theme can be assessed with mind maps, open-ended questions, checklists, worksheets, diagnostic tree, performance tasks, matching questions, true-false questions, analytical and holistic rubrics.

A performance task can be given to convert time, length, mass and currency units among themselves. This assignment can be assessed with an analytical rubric. A holistic rubric can be used to reveal students' estimation skills.

In the 2018 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum in Table 1, practitioners are provided with guidance on the general assessment and evaluation of all subjects. For example, “The curriculum does not draw strict boundaries for practitioners in terms of assessment tools and methods that can be used in the assessment process, it only guides them. However, the required technical and academic standards should be followed in the preferred assessment and evaluation tool and method.” is one of these items. Assessment and evaluation tools and methods are not included in accordance with the characteristics of the subjects. In the 2024 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum, appropriate assessment and evaluation are provided for each of the subjects in grades 1, 2, 3, and 4. The tools and methods required for the assessment and evaluation of all subjects are provided in detail. When Table 2 is examined, examples of tools and equipment suitable for measuring and evaluating the learning outcomes of the relevant theme such as “Mind maps, open-ended questions, checklists, worksheets, diagnostic tree, performance tasks, matching questions, true-false questions, analytical and holistic rubrics” are seen.

CONCLUSION

The 2018 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum has a well-prepared assessment and evaluation section for grades 1, 2, 3, and 4. For example, “The curriculum does not draw definite boundaries for implementers in terms of assessment tools and methods that can be used in the assessment process, it only guides them. However, the required technical and academic standards should be followed in the preferred assessment and evaluation tool and method” (Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Turkey, 2018) has guided implementers. In assessment and evaluation, it is very valuable to provide general guidance on the extent to which the desired characteristics of the student can be achieved. In this sense, it increases efficiency in education and serves as a guide for implementers. According to the 2018 program, the 2024 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum is seen to provide detailed information on various tools and methods suitable for the subjects in 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th grades. In this sense, the 2024 Program is thought to be better. It is seen that the assessment and evaluation techniques in the courses in university teacher training programs are limited to only traditional tools or methods. (Gelbal and Kelecioğlu, 2007). In this case, the teacher may be inadequate in terms of accessing and applying the necessary assessment tools with the developing technology. However, according to the 2018 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum, the 2024 Primary School Mathematics Curriculum has completely guided the implementers in terms of providing the assessment and evaluation tools and methods that should be applied separately for each subject. The teacher is not left alone in deciding which type of assessment and tool to use for which subject. The detailed presentation of various tools and methods appropriate for the subjects in the Primary School Mathematics Course Curriculum in Grades 1, 2, 3 and 4 may increase the teacher's knowledge about assessment and evaluation and deepen this knowledge.

REFERENCES

- B. Kiral, "2023 Evaluation of The 2023 Education Vision Document In Terms of Character Education", *Journal of National Education* vol.49, no.225, (2020), pp. 5-22.
- C. M. Plaza, J. R. Draugalis,, M. K. Slack, G. H. Skrepnek, and K. A. Sauer, "Curriculum Mapping in Program Assessment and Evaluation, *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education* Vol.71, No 2, (2007), pp.1-8.
- J. T. Dillon (2009) *The questions of curriculum*, *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, Vol.41, No3,(2009), pp.343-359.
- M. Özenç, "Determination of Levels of Primary School Teachers' Alternative Assessment and Evaluation Knowledge" *Dicle University Journal of Education* vol.21 (2013) pp.157-178.
- Ministry of National Education of Republic of Türkiye, "Primary mathematic Curriculum(1.,2., 3, 4. Grades)" (2018) <https://mufredat.meb.gov.tr/>
- Ministry of National Education of Republic of Türkiye, "Primary mathematic Curriculum(1.,2., 3, 4. Grades)" (2024) <https://mufredat.meb.gov>
- N. Mamur, "Assessment and Assessment in Visual Art Education", *Pamukkale University Journal of Education* vol. 28, (2010), pp. 175-188.
- K. Struyven, F. Dochy and S. Janssens, "Students' perceptions about evaluation and assessment in higher education:a review" *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, Vol. 30, No. 4, (2005), pp. 325–341.
- S. Gelbal and H. Kelecioğlu, "Teachers' Proficiency Perceptions of about The Assessment and Evaluation Techniques and The Problems They Confront" *H. U. Journal of Education* vol 33, (2007), pp, 135-145.
- Y. Chen, L. B. Hoshower (2003) "Student Evaluation of Teaching Effectiveness: An assessment of student perception and motivation", *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, Vol.28 No.1, (2003), pp.71-88.